

UNDERTREES

AGROFORESTRY RESEARCH

H2020-MSCA-RISE 2019 UNDERTREES

Creating knowledge for UNDERstanding ecosystem seRvicEs of agroforEstry systems through a holistic methodological framework

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Abbreviation list

Acronyms Explanation	
ESR	Early-Stage Researcher
KER	Key Exploitable Results
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SSSA	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna
WP	Work Package
PMB	Project Management Board
DEP	Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Executive Summary

This deliverable (D6.1) includes a detailed Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (DEP) of the UNDERTREES Project. All the dissemination and exploitation activities are thoroughly described throughout the stages of the project and towards the various targeted recipients to raise awareness and participation. Key elements are peer-reviewed articles in international high-impact journals, green and gold open access publishing policy, contributions to conferences and workshops, including the planning of sessions at flagship conferences. The implementation of these activities is coordinated by the Project Management Board (PMB). Regarding the exploitation of results, the main objective of UNDERTREES is to foster intersectoral cross-country knowledge exchange, thus secondments will ensure interactions among sectors and across borders, fostering a large international collaboration.

Introduction

The overarching objective of UNDERTREES is to form an international and inter-sectoral network of 15 organisations in 3 continents (Europe, Africa and South America) working on a joint research programme in the field of agroforestry (AF) and ecosystem services (ES) assessment. The participants are academic, government institutions and enterprises that will exchange skills and knowledge to progress towards key advances in agroforestry systems evaluation and design, while enhancing collaborative research and staff exchange across different continents. Skills and knowledge exchanges with African and South America countries, where agroforestry has a sound historical role in fostering environmental and socio-economical sustainability, will advance agroforestry systems comprehension, with significant benefits for the European environment and society. The staff members in the project will develop new skills, will be exposed to new research environments and will have their career perspectives widened. To achieve its aim, UNDERTREES identified research, training, and participatory activities at 16 study sites in 5 biogeographical areas, within three thematic areas: (1) agronomic and environmental sustainability, (2) socio-economic sustainability and (3) policy development. UNDERTREES will advance research by strengthening intersectoral cross-country collaboration, will provide training and education at academic and technical level, and will engage with local, national and international stakeholders to create shared knowledge on agroforestry ES for EU agricultural policy development.

UNDERTREES strategy for dissemination and exploitation

The overall objective of D6.1 (linked to Task 6.1: Dissemination and Exploitation strategy) is to develop a Dissemination and Exploitation plan (DEP) that will not only secure the promotion of project results to specialists via specific scientific channels, but also identify and reach out all stakeholders, including end users, the public, data driven industries, policy makers and regulators etc., in order to raise their awareness on the findings of UNDERTREES.

To achieve this, a detailed DEP has been developed. To a certain extent, this DEP has been already implemented and, as the present deliverable comprises DEP’s first version, it will be updated and adopted throughout the subsequent stages of the UNDERTREES project, if necessary. The overall aim of the DEP is to create impact that will outlast the project by making the results of UNDERTREES research known to anyone who could benefit from them.

Additionally, the dissemination and outreach strategy aims at achieving the following objectives:

- Maximizing the outreach of the project itself and of project results.
- Maximizing the visibility of the project at European scale.
- Establishing communities of interested stakeholders.
- Maximizing the potential for exploitation of project results, through the use of state-of-the-art communication tools directed at relevant stakeholder groups.
- Maximizing the interaction between UNDERTREES Research and Training and society at large.

Dissemination strategy

The key element of the strategy is to increase dissemination progressively to ensure a wide awareness of the project and foster favourable conditions for the uptake of its results, also considering that non-academic partners offer a unique avenue to transfer research results to the market, internalizing them in their products and practices. The dissemination strategy utilizes the key elements of the communication content (website and social media) focusing on the following target groups: (1) scientific communities; (2) the public (including vulnerable groups such as minors and elders, educating communities); (3) policy makers and (4) regulators. A detailed description of all the key elements and components of the dissemination strategy is presented hereafter.

Communication Content

Website

The UNDERTREES Project website (www.undertrees.eu) has been launched in M34. It serves as a central portal for the project and its individual projects, providing information about the consortium, and research outputs. The website is updated regularly, with sections such as “results” addressing UNDERTREES topics and outputs.

Social media

Social media have become a very popular means of disseminating information fast across heterogeneous target groups. These channels serve on-demand access to content anytime, anywhere, on any digital device. To extend the project target audience (especially to involve the greater public and not only sectoral experts), UNDERTREES is integrating these media tools strategically in the communication activities. Twitter and Facebook (Table 1) have been selected as the most appropriate social networks to promote the project achievements, news, and outcomes. The Early-Stage Researcher (ESR), under the guidance of the project’s PMB, will act as moderator of all social profiles, controlling and filtering inadequate contents and monitoring the suitability and relevance of the information to be published.

Table 1 Social Media activated in UNDERTREES

TWITTER	
	<p>Use of Twitter will be focused on broadcasting relevant news, calls, events and beneficiaries and partners activity, in real-time whenever possible (i.e. live action of an UNDERTREES partner in an external event). Target audience: experts</p> <p>Link: https://twitter.com/RISE_UNDERTREES</p>
FACEBOOK	
	<p>Use of Facebook will be focused on broadcasting relevant news, calls, events and beneficiaries and partners activity, in real-time whenever possible (i.e. live action of an UNDERTREES partner in an external event). Target audience: non-experts</p> <p>Link: https://www.facebook.com/projectundertrees</p>

Beneficiaries’ websites

Most beneficiaries have regular posts on their own websites or social media. We will disseminate the activities of the project regularly and frequently also via these channels. Additionally, a general description of UNDERTREES will be created in all beneficiaries’ websites as a static information point, that will be linked to UNDERTREES official website, as a dynamic information repository.

Internal communication

The mode of internal communication respects the rules provided under the Data Management Plan (deliverable D6.1) and shall be applicable for any internal communication.

Communication strategy

Targeted strategies for communication, dissemination, and exploitation of project results will be directed by PMB, in full respect of other legitimate interests (such as trade secrets, personal data protection, etc.).

Due to the diverse nature of the project community, different communication activities and channels, both electronic/online and face-to-face, will be utilized. Communication in and around the project will be organized at four distinct levels:

- Between beneficiaries, e.g., regular Microsoft Teams videocalls, emails, face-to-face project meetings and workshops.
- Towards stakeholders closely involved with the project.
- Towards the general public, the scientific community, decision and policy-makers, and the business community.
- Towards the EU Commission Services, e.g., email and phone calls with project officer, regular reports, deliverables, etc.

Any **external communication** will acknowledge the funding from the European Union and the association of the UNDERTREES project to the MSCA actions through the following information/items:

- A dedicated sentence to acknowledge funding: “The author/s is/are part of UNDERTREES project. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872384” and the EU flag.

Visual identity of the project

An easily recognizable (visual) identity of the project is essential to achieve best communication results. A set of visual tools has been identified and made available to the beneficiaries and partners for use in communication and dissemination activities.

Visual tools:

- Project logo (in English): see **Annex 1**.
- Templates (for PowerPoint presentations, scientific conference presentations, policy briefs, papers,

H2020 reports/deliverables, etc.)

- Project website (in English).
- Link to the project website and/or reference to the project (in English and/or national languages) in the beneficiaries’ institutional websites.
- Grant Agreement number – Beneficiaries are requested to use the project GA number in all their external communication and dissemination materials, together with the EU flag and the following accompanying text: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872384”.

Towards to the scientific community

The dissemination strategy towards the scientific and research community mainly includes submission of papers to leading peer-reviewed journals, and presentations at selected conferences and workshops.

International scientific conferences

Participants will disseminate project results at relevant scientific conferences organized on an annual or bi-annual basis in the target fields, e.g.: EURAF – European Agroforestry Federation congress, The World Agroforestry Congress, European Grassland Federation congress.

ESRs will be encouraged to participate in these outreach events as a means to practically acquire communication skills.

Scientific publications

Project results will be published in international high-impact peer-reviewed journals, upon a green or gold open access publishing policy. These journals will be either general (e.g., Scientific Reports; Plos One), or specialized (e.g., Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment; Agroforestry Systems; Agronomy for Sustainable Development; Agricultural Systems).

Impact and Exploitation Strategy

Dissemination activities are considered of primary importance for the UNDERTREES consortium since the impact of the project can only be meaningful if results are widely communicated to all the targeted audiences (as described in the previous section) and exploited to the utmost extent. Thus, in the frame of the exploitation strategy, it is important to map the impact that this project could have at the levels of society, school, and research and technological development. An Innovation Management approach to manage the exploitation of the project outcomes has been planned in conjunction with the allocation of responsibilities to all the involved beneficiaries and upon certain follow up activities implemented throughout the duration of the project and beyond, as stipulated in articles 28 and 29 of the Model Grant Agreement.

Innovation Management

The project’s innovation management process will be based on identifying, collecting, describing, and working towards channelling creative ideas stemming from key WPs into innovative valuable propositions in terms of guidelines and policy directives.

Follow-up activities

Each partner undertakes the responsibility to contribute to the various dissemination and communication activities on a regular basis, such as providing inputs for the project **social media and website**. Additionally, after the ESRs’ boarding on the project, regular publication of papers (in peer reviewed journals, conferences etc.) has been scheduled with a minimum of **1 publication in Conferences, 1 participation in Workshops, and 1 publication submitted to a peer review journal per ESR during the project**.

As project results often continue to grow and remain important even after the end date of the project, it is crucial to ensure their follow up and monitoring for demonstrating the European research value, the creation of impact on society and further strengthening the European Research Area. Within the frame of the obligations of H2020 beneficiaries after the end of the project, as stipulated in articles 28 and 29 of the Model Grant Agreement, project outcomes and results will continue to be exploited and disseminated up to four years after the end of the project. To do so, there will be continuous reporting under the Funding and Tenders Portal module even after the end of the project.

Additionally, the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) of the project (guidelines, policy recommendations) will be published on the Horizon Results Platform. In addition, dedicated and tailored support to better exploit the results of UNDERTREES will be sought through the Horizon Results Booster, the Commission’s free consulting service to assist in D&E activities. Services that will be utilized will include the clustering of projects for common dissemination, enhanced exploitation plans, business plans for R&I results and commercialisation services for the more mature results.

Finally, open access to scientific publications and the research data funded by the Framework Programme will be provided (Article 29.2 & 29.3). In this respect, project results will be published on the Commission’s open access publishing platform, Open Research Europe and European Open Science Cloud, services for Horizon 2020 and future Horizon Europe beneficiaries.

¹¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/mga/gga/h2020-mga-gga-multi_en.pdf

Responsibilities

1. SSSA holds the responsibility for strategies related to communications, dissemination and exploitation of the project results.

Cost of Dissemination and Communication Activities

Generally, it is hard to predict the cost of these activities, as many of them are an integral part of standard research activities. Ideally, it is necessary to estimate the time or cost needed for activities related to data collection, data entry and transcription, data validation and documentation and the cost of preparing data for archiving and re-use. Those resources that include time and effort costs, i.e., search costs, maintenance of technical infrastructure, individual preparation effort needed to use the infrastructure etc. are the so-called non-monetary costs.

Conclusions

This document presented a comprehensive overview of the dissemination and public engagement activities that will be conducted by the project in order to raise awareness and interest on the project itself. The dissemination strategy includes a common project reference identity, specific tools adapted to selected target groups, and a well-established communication policy. The DEP includes several activities and tools that will maximize the communication with stakeholders and dissemination of the results.

To further improve the dissemination strategy, the DEP will be regularly reviewed and properly updated during the project lifetime.

List of Annexes

Annex 1 - Project logos

Annex 1 – Project logos

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